

INDIRECT TRANSLATION: FROM LATIN TO JAPANESE TO CHINESE USING DUTCH TRANSLATION METHODS BY THE JAPANESE SCHOLAR, RYŌTAKU MAENO

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During the Edo period (1603-1868), Japan had contact with only a few countries, one of which was the Netherlands. Japanese scholars of Western knowledge learned Dutch due to this Dutch influence. Ryōtaku Maeno (1723-1803), a leading scholar of Dutch, was asked by the *Shogun*, the ruler of Japan, to translate some Western captions that corresponded to some images. These captions were written in a Western language that was not Dutch. In fact, they were written in Latin. Maeno had never studied Latin. In addition, there was no one who could teach Maeno Latin at that time. He knew that he did not have the ability to translate the captions. However, Maeno was unable to reject the order from the *Shogun*.

In this hopeless situation, surprisingly Maeno completed the translation in 1779. Maeno's translation was named *Seiyō Gasan Yakubunkō*. This was likely the first translation of Latin poetry by a Japanese person. He translated nine Latin captions. Maeno decided to translate three of them into the style of Chinese tetrasyllabic poems, similar to the poems in *Shijing*, the oldest anthology of Chinese poetry. He also quoted passages and words from *Shijing* in his translations.

How did Maeno translate Latin into Chinese? He did it through indirect translation. To aid in this process, he referred to a Latin-Dutch dictionary. He also used the same method which he had previously used in translating Dutch into Japanese. The first step Maeno completed was the translation from Latin into Japanese based on his knowledge of Dutch. Then, he used his Japanese translation to create the Chinese poetic translation. In short, he translated Latin into Chinese by himself, but it was an indirect translation mediated through his Japanese translation. I will explain this extremely complicated process of indirect translation at the conference.